

PERSONALITY IN TEACHING THE MODULE OF LATIN AND MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN THE MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

Makhmudov Zafar Mardanovich

Assistant of the department of Languages, Samarkand state medical university,

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9631-6116>

e-mail: maxmudovzafar4510@gmail.com

Omonova Mokhigul

Student of the Faculty of Pediatrics, Samarkand State Medical University

moxigul660@gmail.com

Abstracts: This article was written on the example of the work carried out at the University on the essence of education aimed at the student's personality in the teaching of the Latin language and the module of medical terminology in a medical higher education institution.

Key words: education, personality, student, medical terminology, latin, pedagogical technology, communicative, lesson.

“Not knowing - not scary, but scary - not learning”. Chinese wisdom.

Introduction: Education aimed at the student's personality implies the organization of a pedagogical environment adapted to the personal capabilities of the student, as well as the educational process. In this educational technology, it is of great importance to understand, respect, trust each student. Student - teacher and student-student cooperation will give the intended positive results.

Informations and methods. Communicative techniques are widely used in this technology, let's look at some of their main signs.

There are the following basic criteria for the implementation of Education directed by the teacher to the student's personality:

1. To look at each student as a great person, respect him, understand him, accept him, trust him.
2. It is necessary to create such an atmosphere of education in which the student will feel that he is a person, feel the attention to him.

3. Not to put pressure on the student, and not exaggerate his shortcomings, to identify the reasons for his lack of knowledge, to behave badly, and to eliminate them in such a way as not to harm the student's personality.

4. Organizing an “atmosphere of success” in education, helping the student to succeed in his studies, gaining confidence in his own strength and talent. To mean to the student that each of those around him is like himself, in which he develops a sense of involvement in the team.

5. To gain the respect and trust of the student, to look at himself from the point of view of the individual as well.

Lesson form in student personality - oriented education Personality - oriented learning situations are inextricably linked with the methods and methods of organizing the cognitive activity of students. Forms of such training vary. Special attention among them is paid to the research research methods and dialogic forms of teacher - student cooperation in the course of the lesson, as well as visual, pictorial, reproductive and other methods are also used. The forms and methods of such training directly correspond to the concept and principles of the approach to the activities of the individual, they serve to maximize the activation of the student's inner world, thinking and personal life experience. In this place, the educational process, organized in such forms and methods, by directing students to acquire knowledge by stimulating educational activities, remains one of the main sources of the development of personal knowledge, experience and emotions of students.

We will cite some non-traditional lesson forms in which education aimed at the student's personality is carried out:

A diving lesson consists of exercises for the active study of a subject by being in the most comfortable environment to acquire certain knowledge or by creating such an environment.

A competition lesson is an exercise in strengthening knowledge by organizing student cross-competition.

A consultation lesson is the exercise of mastering the lesson through the organization of student consultations and teacher consultations in the course of the lesson.

A creativity lesson is a lesson for organizing independent creativity of students.

A test lesson is a lesson in which students are organized to test their mastery in different forms.

A lesson in expressing doubt is a lesson in explaining a new topic by making rules on the topic of the lesson, interesting arguments and analyzes about what can happen if the conclusions are considered inappropriate.

A creative reports lesson is the presentation of independently learned knowledge and conclusions of students on certain topics.

A generalization lesson is a lesson for conducting exercises to summarize the knowledge gained on previously mentioned topics.

A science fantastic lesson is a lesson in expanding students independent thinking by conducting an exercise in creative fantasy, conjectural thinking based on learned knowledge.

A truth-seeking lesson is a lesson in determining the truth and ensuring the mastery of the topic by organizing independent student feedback on certain issues related to the topic of the lesson.

A "paradoxes" lesson is a lesson for describing the topic under study in connection with various "paradoxes" in order to increase the activity and interests of students, as well as determining the correct conclusions based on conducting appropriate analyzes.

A seminar lesson is a lesson to ensure that all students in the class master the lesson and strengthen their knowledge by listening to information about the results of completing tasks given to students in advance on questions related to the topic of the new lesson.

An excursion lesson is in these classes, it is provided to carry out the work of connecting their knowledge with life and directing students to the profession by taking and introducing them to various objects: museum, shrine, enterprise, workshop, nature objects, scientific institution, College, Lyceum, etc. To objects that are too far away and difficult to go, in cases where there are films, various exhibitions and other materials about them, it is also possible to organize video sessions by instructing and explaining them to students.

Accounting, positivity and development of personal qualities of students. Taking into account the age characteristics of students in the educational process, knowledge of their personal qualities, an individual approach to analysis are derived from the rules and requirements of the current age psychology and pedagogy. One of the main issues in this is to take into account the fact that students differ in their preparation for each other, their interests and different assimilation of subjects. In accordance with this, there are individual approaches of each teacher to achieve the optimal result over a certain period of time, that is, to the extent

foreseen by students, taking into account the difference in teaching style, planning the educational process from each other.

To achieve the goals of positivity and development of these qualities on the basis of taking into account the personal qualities of students, it is required to give students independent tasks in the lesson, organize their independent conclusions, learn from each other, pay special attention to creating a favorable environment for their studies.

Ensuring continuity of education. Ensuring continuity of education with education is one of the issues that are the focus of attention in all times. This requires creating favorable conditions for the speech, communication skills, emotional, mental, physical and social development of students in the educational process, including: a clean place, fresh air, a room with normal temperature and sufficient lighting in it, attention to safety, Sports, Recreation, adequate equipment of playgrounds, etc.

Breakthrough technology and Werner Erhard school. This technology consists of manager retraining readings, the purpose of which is precisely to awaken the abilities and aspirations of each individual person existing in their inner world (but stifled by everyday monotonous life and work) to everyday searches to solve traditional problems as a new problem. These courses consist of a large number of activities developed to overcome personal stereotypes of the listener's thinking and behavior, to activate and modify their capabilities and ways to solve outdated problems in a new way.

The advantages of these courses - aimed at employing the human factor, do not require the expenditure of special funds; the achieved effect does not fade, that is, the obtained effect provides several times with regular intensification in new forms and conditions; consists in the creation of separate major innovations, the search for unconventional ways out of the resulting dead ends.

Courses and seminars in 48 directions are conducted in 94 cities in the United States and 128 cities in other countries. These courses are attended by 57,000 people per year.

Educational intensification technology based on models of educational material consisting of schemes and conditional signs (base signal synopsis) (V. F. Shatalov). The synopsis of the base signals consists of visual schemes, in which the information units to be mastered are reflected, various dependencies are indicated between them, and the classification of abstract (abstract) material on the significance of signs and goals for evocative examples, experiments are given with different conditional signs.

When working with the synopsis of base signals, a number of specific methods and methodological solutions are used.

Issues of the practical use of education aimed at the student's personality. At the Department of languages of Samarkand State Medical University, in the implementation of education aimed at the student Person of teachers on a pedagogical team scale, the study of the student's personality is carried out from time to time in order to take into account differences in the level of knowledge, interests, different assimilation of subjects in the lesson, create a favorable environment, In this case, it is recommended to conduct training according to existing conditions and opportunities in any of the forms such as debating, training, performance game or seminar. To improve the effectiveness of education aimed at the student's personality, building on the following theories gives good results:

Theory of the development of student intelligence. This theory was developed by the Swiss psychologist Jean Piaget (1896-1980). This theory has become of great importance for understanding the development of student intelligence. According to him, many features of student thinking were revealed. These are: egocentrism - inability to move to the point of view of another person; syncretism-a type of thinking in which a tendency is formed to correlate various phenomena without an adequate internal basis; transduction is a feature of logical thinking, in which a transition is carried out, from private to private, excluding generality; artificialism - the perception of the universe as if it were created by human hands, as artificial; animism - the perception of the universe as living, not noticing contradictions.

In conclusion, it can be said that in the educational process, it is necessary to plan activities that correspond to the level of development of the student and contribute to his logical, mental and personal growth.

Theory of the nearest area of development. The theory was developed by Russian psychologist Lev Semyonovich Vygotsky (1896-1934). According to this theory, education should go ahead and follow the development of the student to himself.

Development is formed only when the student has mastered new skills. But, it is obliged to master it not in isolation from real life, but on the basis of the knowledge that it has. This became known as “the nearest area of development” and expanded into pedagogy and psychology.

As the nearest Development Area, is L.S.Vigotsky had explained “functions in the maturation process, maturing tomorrow, in the now emerging state, not calling them the fruit of development, development buds, flowers, that is, functions that are just maturing”.

The nearest area of development is determined in the process of the student solving difficult issues for his age when he has the help of an older person. For example, for a baby who has learned to crawl, crawling is the skill he has mastered, but standing and walking are the skills that are now learned by him and learned with the help of seniors, a skill that is considered in the student's closest area of development.

Conclusions and suggestions. In communication with the student, the expected result is achieved by finding characters whose closest area of development is wide, based on his interests, and gradually replenishing them with new knowledge. In this case, friendship and mutual respect for students are the main prerequisites.

LITERATURES:

1. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2022). The place of problematic and heuristic methods in the process of teaching latin and medical terminology.

2. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции— знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).

3. Maxmudov, Z. M. Lotin tili va tibbiyot terminologiyasi fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan unumli foydalanish istiqbollari. *Urganch davlat universiteti, "Ilm sarchashmalari*, 118-120.

4. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2022). Teaching correct pronunciation of latin as an international language of medicine in medical education institutions, Global Technovation 5th International Multidisciplinary Scientific Conference Hosted From Paris, France. *March 30th*, 30-31.

5. Maxmudov, Z. M. Retsept yozishda duch kelinadigan ayrim muammolarning qonuniy yechimi va amalda qo'llash haqida ba'zi mulohazalar,“. *O'zbekistonda ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqotlar*” mavzusidagi.

6. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2021). Bobur Salimovich Sharipov Lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning didaktik tamoyillari va uning asosi haqida fikrlar. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 6.

7. Omonova, M., & Makhmudov, Z. (2023). MODERN SIGNS OF USING THE QUINCE PLANT IN FOLK MEDICINE. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(4), 41–45. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/1002>

8. Qurbonova, Z., & Maxmudov, Z. (2023). LOTIN TILIDA KLINIK TERMINLARNING TO'G'RI QO'LLANISH YUZASIDAN FIKRLAR. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3 Part 3), 23–27. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11503>

9. Arziqulova Ozoda, & Maxmudov Zafar Mardanovich. (2023). NA'MATAK – BEBAHO NE'MAT. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(9), 301–306. Retrieved from <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/7722>

10. Махмудов, З. М., & Шарипов, Б. С. Талабаларнинг фанни яхши ўрганишлари учун психо–эмоционал таъсир этишда халқ мақол ва маталларидан тўғри фойдаланиш (лотин тили ва tibbiy терминология фани мисолида). *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 112.

11. Maxmudov, Z. M. (2022). Lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiyani o'rganishda o'zbek tili grammatikasining o'rni. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 756-759.

12. Maxmudov Zafar Mardanovich. (2023). LOTIN TILINING ZAMONAVIY TILLARGA BEVOSITA VA BILVOSITA TA'SIRI. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(6), 132–136. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/288>

13. Maxmudov, Z. (2022). RETSEPTURADA ERITMALARNING QO'LLANILISHI YUZASIDAN AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(6), 524–527. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/2248>

14. Maxmudov, Z. (2023). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA YUNON KLINIK VA FARMATSEVTIK ATAMALARINING QO'LLANILISHI. *Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi*, (9), 263-269.

15. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). ABOUT SOME METHODS OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(10), 245-249. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049492>

16. Makhmudov, Z., Tuychiyev, K., & Usmanov, S. (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE-THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(13), 20-26.

17. Makhmudov, Z. ., Tuychiyev, K., & Usmanov, S. . (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE - THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences*, 2(13), 20–26. извлечено от <http://econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/7225>

18. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF INSURED MEDICINE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHARMACY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 185-190.

19. Salimovich, Sharipov & Mardanovich, Makhmudov. (2020). Linguistic views on french lexical and phraseological antonyms linguistic description of the phenomenon of antonymy. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. 10. 775-780. 10.5958/2249-7137.2020.01431.7.

20. Aytmuratova P.G. Beknazarova M.K., Makhmudov Z.M., THE MAIN METHODS OF FORENG LANGUAGE TEACHING, *ACADEMICIA An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 10, Issue 11, https://saarj.com/academicia-past-issue-2020/#tabs_desc_5155_11

21. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PRACTICAL CLASSES OF THE SUBJECT” LATIN LANGUAGE AND MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 369-375.

22. Omonova, M., & Makhmudov , Z. (2023). MODERN SIGNS OF USING THE QUINCE PLANT IN FOLK MEDICINE. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and*

Clinical Research, 3(4), 41–45. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/1002>

23. Qurbonova, Z., & Maxmudov, Z. (2023). LOTIN TILIDA KLINIK TERMINLARNING TO'G'RI QO'LLANISH YUZASIDAN FIKRLAR. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(3 Part 3), 23–27. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/11503>

24. Arziqulova Ozoda, & Maxmudov Zafar Mardanovich. (2023). NA'MATAK – BEBAHO NE'MAT. *Scientific Impulse*, 1(9), 301–306. Retrieved from <http://nauchniyimpuls.ru/index.php/ni/article/view/7722>

25. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2022). The place of problematic and heuristic methods in the process of teaching latin and medical terminology.

26. Maxmudov, Z. M. Lotin tili va tibbiyot terminologiyasi fanini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan unumli foydalanish istiqbollari. *Urganch davlat universiteti, "Ilm sarchashmalari*, 118-120.

27. Maxmudov, Z. (2023). LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA DARSLARIDA YUNON KLINIK VA FARMATSEVTIK ATAMALARINING QO'LLANILISHI. *Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi*, (9), 263-269.

28. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). ABOUT SOME METHODS OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(10), 245-249. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049492>

29. Makhmudov, Z., Tuychiyev, K., & Usmanov, S. (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE-THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(13), 20-26.

30. Makhmudov, Z. ., Tuychiyev, K., & Usmanov, S. . (2023). SOME OF THE MOST USED FORMS OF MEDICINE IN MEDICAL PRACTICE - THE USE OF TABLETS AND SOLUTIONS. *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences*, 2(13), 20–26. извлечено от <http://econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/7225>

31. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF INSURED MEDICINE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHARMACY IN UZBEKISTAN. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 185-190.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

32. Mardanovich, M. Z. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PRACTICAL CLASSES OF THE SUBJECT” LATIN LANGUAGE AND MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 369-375.

33. Karimovna, Y. S., & Rashid, A. (2023, November). ANATOMICAL TERMINOLOGY. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 101-104). K

34. Karimovna, Y. S., & Zara, A. (2023). EXPLORING THE LATIN ROOTS OF CHEMICAL TERMINOLOGY: NAMES OF CHEMICAL ELEMENTS, ACIDS, AND OXIDES. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 8-13. K

35. Orova, S., & Nasimova, S. ELECTRONIC COLLECTED MATERIALS OF XI JUNIOR RESEARCHERS'CONFERENCE 2019 Linguistics, literature, philology 7 UDC 372.881 THE WAYS OF TEACHING LANGUAGES AT MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS Samarkand State Medical Institute. Y

36. Karimovna, Y. S., & Zulkarnain, S. (2023, November). DEGREES OF COMPARISON OF ADJECTIVES AND COORDINATION WITH NOUNS OF FIFTH DECLENSION. In *Konferensiyalar| Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 80-82). K

37. Karimovna, Y. S. (2022). The linguistic environment in the field of medical communications. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(2), 143-147. K

38. Karimovna, Y. S. Social-cultural Characteristics of Uzbek and English Medical Speech. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(5), 294-298. K

39. Karimovna, Y. S., & Farxodovna, R. K. VISION. THE MAIN VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN ADOLESCENTS. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych.*, 45. K

40. Ченых, Е. С. 12 (69), 2019 LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MEDICAL Y

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

INSTITUTIONS Nuritdinova Zulkhumor Shamsievna Head of Chair in Samarkand State Medical Institute. *Yorova Sayora Karimovna English teacher of Samarkand State Medical Institute*, 9, 26.

41.

K

arimovna, Y. S., Erkinovna, T. N., & Agwan, A. (2023). MODERN EDUCATION AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT NURTURING GLOBAL CITIZENS IN THE 21ST CENTURY. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(11), 292-294.